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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ROLE STRESS ABOUT GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE HOSPITAL NURSES IN CHENNAI

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Nursing professionals of government and private Hospitals. They were administered Organizational Role Stress Scale by Pareek (1981) in order to assess the level of stress experienced by them. The obtained results Stress has become the most important factor influencing individual efficacy and satisfaction in modern day occupational settings. In this context, the nursing profession is increasingly characterized by occupational stress. This study was conducted with the aim of investigating the effect of role stress in a sample of 120 revealed that male nurses experienced significantly higher stress level as compared to females. Second, male nurses from private hospitals showed significantly higher level of stress levels than the government nurses on eight out of the ten dimensions of Organizational Role Stress Scale.

Introduction

Role Stress and its Types in the Nursing Profession

Nurses confront stark suffering, grief and death as few other people do. Their nursing tasks are mundane and unrewarding; many are by normal standards, distasteful and disgusting. Others are often degrading; some are simply frightening' (Hingley 1984). In the western scenario a few studies have attempted to measure this stress level but not much has been done in India. *The Times of India* (2005) reported that more than one million new and replacement nurses will be needed by 2012 and Indian nurses (male and female) are very much in demand abroad. This confirms the need to study this group of work force.

As per the International Labor Organization (ILO) manual the role of Nursing is associated with multiple and conflicting demands imposed by Nurse Supervisors and managers, and by medical and administrative staff (Cox T. et al. 1996). This situation appears to lead to work overload and possible to role conflict. One form of such conflict often stated in surveys of nurses relates to the conflict inherent in the instrumental and goal-oriented demands of 'getting the patient better' and those related to providing emotional support and relieving patient stress. In this context, the nursing profession is becoming increasingly characterized by job stress, frequent job turnover and job dissatisfaction (Cooper 1986; Hawley 1992). Nurses also attend to the emotional needs of patients and their families that puts extra load of emotional stress on them.

Nurses now have greater management responsibilities at both the ward. And hospital levels

(Medical Services Development Committee 1995). The major reason is that the management role is so alien to medical professionals that they are more stressed out with the additional workload. The developments in medical science and technology, rapid patient turnover, the rising dependency level of patients, and the emergence of professionalism have increased the complexity and volume of nursing care. Another difficulty faced by nurses in the ward is increased demand for administrative accountability. The nurses have to produce more statistics and written reports of their activities in the ward. They often feel torn between spending time in direct patient care and administrative activities and have they had to perform a great amount of administrative duties asserted that on the ward (Mok and Chan 1996).

In the light of above factors it is important to understand the meaning of stress and organizational role stress, in this group of professionals. Stress is a state of mind, which effects certain biochemical reactions in the human body and is projected by a sense of anxiety. Environmental events or social conditions that have the potential to induce stress are known as 'social stressors'. The factors such as motivation to work, feeling of commitment, organization's culture and identification with the organization play an important role in the perception of stress. Most of the time these psychological factors do not yield satisfactory results and increasing complexities of organizational life become a great source of stress. Stress in the environment is detrimental to the cognitive smoking, and inability to relax. All these factors collectively lead to lowering of work efficiency of any individual.

Research indicates that persons with high personal stress index tend to perform more poorly, have higher absenteeism, and change more jobs frequently than persons who experience fewer stressful life events. Thus, stress influences the job performance negatively. It emerges that the major causes for role stress in any job are: (a) work overload, (b) time pressures, (c) poor quality of supervision, (d) insecure job climate, (e) inadequate authority to match responsibilities (f) role conflict and role ambiguity. As the ILO (1999) study indicated that a broad and growing range of occupations are prone to work related stress. The list included those occupations which equal or exceed the rating of 6 on a stress rating scale of 0 to 10. Nursing profession ranked twelfth (rating-6.5 and was just two levels below doctors (6.8) who were ranked tenth among the top twenty stressful occupations. Kerr et al. (2000) found that nurse workload and nurse health indicators are key factors that must be addressed in developing effective workplace health care. Despite such public recognition for the importance of their role, nurses find themselves working in rapidly changing work environments at the same time that their functions are undergoing significant changes.

The combination of increased workloads, increased patient awareness, uncertain work environments, and an aging nursing workforce could have a major effect on the health of the nurses. To date, there has been no overall synthesis of this multi-dimensional phenomenon, so there was a need to further investigate the health of nurses. The role of nursing is associated with multiple and conflicting demands imposed by nurse supervisors and managers, and by medical and administrative staff. Such a situation appears to lead to work overload and possible to role conflict. Role conflict of this kind may be most obvious when dealing with patients who are critically ill and dying. Indeed, one of the areas of nursing that has attracted particular attention has been critical or intensive care nursing. However the nurses in other areas also experience high stress levels. The studies on stress in nursing have attempted to measure, or have speculated on, the effects of such stress on nurses' health and well-being. There appears to be a general agreement that the experience of work-related stress. Generally detracts from the quality of nurses' working lives, increases minor

Psychiatric morbidity and may contribute to some forms of physical illness, with particular reference to muscular-skeletal problems, stress and depression. Chang et al. (2005) conducted an elaborate study on this topic, on factors related to role stress in nurses and presented strategies for addressing this issue based on the findings of their review while considering potential areas for development and research. Computerized databases were searched as well as hand searching of articles was done in order to conduct this elaborate review. This review identified multiple factors related to the experience of role stress in nurses. Role stress, in

particular, work overload, has been reported as one of the main reasons for nurses leaving the workforce. This study concludes that it is a priority to find new and innovative ways of supporting nurses in their experience of role stress.

Dodd-McCue et al. (2005) examined the role stress and work attitudes of critical care nurses involved in potential organ donation cases. The research examined whether the improved procedure or protocol could positively affect nurses' perceptions of role stress and if so, could the work environment improvements be sustained over time. Survey data were collected at four points over two years. Surveys used previously validated and reliable measures of role stress (role ambiguity, role conflict, role overload) and work attitudes (commitment, satisfaction). Interviews supplemented these data. Results indicated that the nurses' perceptions of role stress associated with potential organ donation cases dramatically dropped after the protocol was implemented. All measures of role stress, particularly role ambiguity and role conflict, showed statistically significant and sustained improvement. Nurses' professional, unit, and hospital commitment and satisfaction reflect an increasingly positive workplace. Thus if roles and procedures are clearly defined the stress level is also reduced.

Parikh et al. (2004) studied occupational stressors and coping mechanisms in nurses. In nurses occupational stress appears to vary according to individual and job characteristics, and work-family conflict. Common occupational stressors found among nurses were workload, role ambiguity, interpersonal relationships and death and dying concerns. Emotional distress, burnout and psychological morbidity could also be a product of occupational stress. Nurses' common coping mechanisms included problem solving, social support and avoidance. Perceived control appeared to be an important mediator of occupational stress. Coping and job satisfaction were found to be reciprocally related. Shift work was highly prevalent among nurses and a significant source of stress. A few studies also attempted to see the effect of organizational setting on role stress in the nurses. Thus in the light of this background the investigator carried out this study with the objective of studying the level of role stress experienced by nurses in government and private hospitals. It was hypothesized that there *Role Stress in Government and Private Hospital Nurses* will be a significant difference among male and female nurses working in government and private hospitals with regard to role stress.

Method: Sample - A sample of 120 nurses from government and private hospitals were selected randomly with equal number of male and females from both the government and private hospitals. The age range was from 20-55 years. All had minimum service of five years and

stress as compared to female nurses.

On the dimension of Inter-role Distance (IRD) the male nurses from Private hospitals (Group B) have mean score of 7.63 which is towards higher side when compared to the other nurse groups (Group A-4.97, Group C-5.53, Group D-6.27). This clearly shows that the male nurses from the private hospitals experience more conflict with their roles as compared to the other groups. Inter-role Distance conflict relates to distance between the organisational role and the other roles. Thus the private hospital nurses feel that they are not able to devote much time to other responsibilities and their family life.

On the next dimension of Role Stagnation (RS) the male nurses from Private hospitals differ significantly from all the three groups. They experience more boredom and feel there is no novelty in their job. More so the male nurses from government hospitals Group A also experience more sense of stagnation as compared to Group C ($t = 2.14$; $p < .05$). The reason for this difference may be that the male nurses need more challenging jobs as compared to female nurses. As the individual grows physically, he or she also wishes to grow in the role the individual occupies in an organisation. Individuals expect to learn new things, take up challenging tasks, prepare for higher responsibilities, etc., in case the role does not provide such opportunities, the individual experiences Role Stagnation. This becomes an acute problem especially when an individual has occupied a role for a long time and keeps performing the same routine functions.

On the dimension of Role Expectation Conflict (REC) there is only gender difference as both the male nurses (government and private) show significant differences ($t = 2.30$; $p < .05$; $t = 3.27$; $p < .01$) when compared to female nurses. They experience more role expectation conflict as they are not able to satisfy the wishes of the many significant people. There may be conflicting expectations from the superiors, subordinates, peers, or clients which they are unable to comply with. The female nurses of both the government and private hospital have no difference as they have same mean scores (mean = 3.67). This sample of female nurses indicates that they are not dissatisfied with their job role and have accepted it as it is.

Elsewhere in a study by Rizzo et al. (1970) on resident physicians and managers of firms also found significant inverse relationships between perceived role conflict and ambiguity and job satisfaction, organisational commitment and psychological stress. Results showed that role conflict inversely. *Role Stress in Government and Private Hospital Nurses* affected satisfaction in the hospital whereas role ambiguity had inverse effect on satisfaction in the manufacturing firms.

Further examination of the result table shows that the male nurses experience more role erosion as compared to

female nurses. Role Erosion (RE) is a subjective feeling of an individual that some important role expectations he or she has from the role are shared by other roles in the role set. Role erosion is likely to be experienced in an organisation, which is re-defining roles and creating new roles. When a role occupant feels that some functions which he or she would like to perform are being performed by some other role, the stress felt is called Role Erosion. The male nurses experience significantly higher level of role erosion in government ($t = 2.98$; $p < .01$) as well as private ($t = 5.59$; $p < .01$) hospitals. There are differences within the same gender.

When the role occupant feels that there are too many expectations from the significant role senders in the role set, he or she experiences Role Overload (RO). It is experienced when an individual's efficiency level is brought down due to excess workload. On this dimension also both the male nurses differ significantly from the female nurses of government hospitals (AVC, $t = 2.55$, $p < .01$; BVC, $t = -3.60$, $p < .01$). The male nurses have higher mean scores suggesting they are expected to do more in the absence of amount of power and freedom given to them. Gray-Toft and Anderson (1985) have also reported workload as the most frequent cause of stress, particularly among male nurses. Thus we can clearly observe that both government and private male nurses have more role overload in their jobs, as compared to their female counterparts. Thus we can clearly observe that both government and private male nurses have more Role Overload in their jobs, as compared to their female counterparts. Possibly the male nurses have to fulfill too many expectations from the other people in a given role set they play. They are not able to finish their work on time and the amount of work they do interferes with how well it has been done. Role overload also might have occurred as the role occupant has lesser power, than the expected output.

On the dimension of Role Isolation (RI) the main criteria governing the perception of distance are frequency and ease of interaction. When linkages are strong, role isolation will be low. In the absence of strong linkages, role isolation may be high. Role isolation can, therefore, be measured in terms of existing and desired linkages. The gap between desired and actual linkages will indicate the amount of Role Isolation. It is possible that Role Isolation was more in private male nurses, because of the gap between desired and actual linkage will indicate that amount of role isolation in the absence of strong linkage in nurse's role, so isolation was high. Role Isolation refers to the psychological distance between the Occupant's role and other roles in the same role set.

When a role occupant feels that he or she is not prepared (does not have the required competence) to undertake a role effectively, he or she may experience Personal Inadequacy (PI), a kind of stress. The individual may feel he or she does not have enough

knowledge, skills, or training, or has no had time to prepare for the role assigned to him or her. People who are assigned new roles without enough preparation or orientation are also likely to experience such stress. On this dimension again the male nurses of private Hospitals are significantly more stressed out as they have scored much higher than all the other groups. The reason for high stress levels can be that they are given tasks which are beyond their skills. In the present times the role of nurses is expanding and work area is becoming more complex with use of advanced technology which may lead to feeling of inadequacy in the nurses as they need to re-equip themselves with new skills. The private hospital nurses possibly are more pressurized to learn the new ways of working with

Results in increased amount of feeling of inadequacy

The only dimension on which there are no significant differences is Role Ambiguity (RA). Role Ambiguity is experienced by people who occupy roles that have been newly created in the organisation, or roles in organization that are undergoing change (with less clear and concrete activities). Possibly, despite the increase in amount of work and type of responsibilities the nature of work in the basics is the same therefore there is not much confusion about the duties as all the four groups have scored very low on this dimension in comparison to other dimensions. The other two dimensions which show significant differences are Self role Distance (SRD) and Role Inadequacy (RIN). Self-role Distance stress arises out of the conflict between the self-concept and one's expectations from the role as perceived by the role occupant. If a person occupies a role, which they subsequently find conflicting with their self-concept, the people feel this type stress. On this dimension also the private nurses experience very high intensity of stress. Possibly this is in line with the other findings of the study as this group has scored high on the other related dimensions of IIRD and REC.

Another reason for high role stress in male nurses of private hospitals can be lack of definition about the role of in the hospital. In the past, a nurse cared for the non-medical needs, such as providing emotional and physical support. Now there is much overlap in the roles performed by nurses and doctors, resulting in a lack of clarity on the respective roles. There is a great need for doctors to give up certain roles and tasks and to take on higher level roles and tasks, and to 'hand over' some of the clinical decision making to appropriate qualified and trained nurses. A lack of professional recognition of nurses reflects the fundamental differences that exist between bureaucratic and professional modes of work organisation in hospitals (Benson 1973 and Raelin 1986) and bureaucratic structure within the hospital is often not conducive to enhancing job satisfaction and commitment of nurses (Gifford et al. 2002; Bolton 2004).

Thus overall the significant findings indicate higher stress levels of nurses in private hospitals as compared to

government hospital. The major reason could be that private nurses need to be more vigilant and alert as they may lose job more easily as compared to government nurses. The job insecurity, face more competition and more work pressure makes them more stressful in carrying out their jobs. The other significant finding is that males experience more stress levels. This is also in line with the findings of the study by Chopra and Singh (1992). They studied the job satisfaction of 46 Employee State Insurance (ESI) doctors. Female doctors reported more job satisfaction and less job related burnout than males. Being male was the best predictor of job related tensions. Many western studies have also explored similar sources of stress in nurses (Bailey and Walker 1980; Heim 1991; Numerof and Abrams 1984).

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